

PROBLEMS OF MODERN TEACHING OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY UZBEK SCHOOLS.

Erdanov Sobir Xabibullo o'g'li
Sobirjonova Munira Tulqin qizi

Trainee teachers of the Department of Russian language and methods of its teaching of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University named after A.

Kadyri

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783748>

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to modern problems of teaching the Russian language in primary Uzbek schools, where the language of instruction is the Uzbek language. In addition, the article discusses the main trend that characterizes the initial process of learning in a modern school, is the focus of the entire learning process not only on communicating knowledge and instilling skills and abilities in children, but above all on developing the personality of students. In connection with this, it is clear that the special significance of taking into account the mental characteristics of children of primary school age is clear: after all, it is in the primary classes that the foundation for the formation of a new person is laid, and the basis for the subsequent assimilation of knowledge and mastery of skills is created. And also the article talks about the main stages of the practical assimilation of the Russian language by primary school students. And the article also provides for the most problematic and difficult topics for schoolchildren as a complex expression of grammatical meanings at the end; case system; the presence of variable parts of speech; the presence in the structure of the word of prefixes, suffixes, endings; category of verb aspect; unidirectional and multidirectional verbs of motion.

Key words: methodology, system of education and upbringing, problems of education, aspects of teaching, grammatical meanings at the end; case system; the presence of variable parts of speech; the presence in the structure of the word of prefixes, suffixes, endings; category of verb aspect;

Today, we are very aware of the general trend towards a decrease in the quality of teaching the Russian language in schools and other educational institutions. We can identify a number of factors that explain the insufficient quality of Russian language teaching in national schools. It is known that de-Russification began in Uzbekistan in the 1990s, and as a result, the Russian-speaking population began to leave our country. The Russian language has become for us the only foreign language studied in schools and universities of the republic, the number of hours of which allotted for its study has been significantly reduced. Including the number of educational institutions: secondary schools, colleges, universities with the teaching of the Russian language has also sharply decreased. For this reason, today a number of changes are being made to develop the Russian language as a foreign language in our country. From the beginning, we need to start with new ideas and as soon as possible to improve the educational process in teaching the Russian language in primary schools. Long-term experience of teaching the Russian language suggests that the problem of fluency in Russian will not be solved without the practical orientation of teaching primary school students and until students in the lower grades acquire strong skills of correct, conscious,

fluent and expressive reading. For this, it is necessary to pay special attention to primary school education, when children are interested in learning. Another big problem is that some teachers do not know how to bring new material to students, so students will not be able to master the necessary knowledge base of elementary school, and they gradually lose interest in the Russian language. Classes in the primary grades should ensure the unity of grammatical and lexical work that connects all types of speech activity, and should also be full of new game methods that will help students in mastering the topic being studied. It is necessary in the classroom to develop in students the skills of expressing thoughts in different forms. This is very helpful conversation on illustrations or descriptions of the picture. And also with the development of coherent speech, translations of small texts from the native language into Russian and the compilation of dialogues on a given topic help well.

Primary classes are considered one of the most important links in the system of public education, and therefore attract special attention from teachers. In recent years, programs, textbooks have been improved, new pedagogical manuals have been issued. In this regard, special attention is paid to the training of primary school teachers.

The main stage in the practical assimilation of the Russian language by students is the elementary school. Psychologists have proved that at primary school age children master a non-native language much faster and better, the language barrier is more easily overcome. Since the task of teaching the Russian language falls on the shoulders of an elementary school teacher, high demands are placed on him. Firstly, an elementary school teacher must be fluent in Russian, have a perfect knowledge of it both theoretically and practically. Secondly, the teacher must know well the psychology of mastering a non-native language, the specifics of the school in which he works, and take into account the interfering influence of the students' native language. In the practical teaching of the Russian language, the selection of the necessary speech material, its arrangement, provision, repetition of words, sample sentences, and grammatical forms are of great importance. At the same time, the leading role belongs to the selection of sentences of the main unit of speech communication, their use in the context, since all aspects of the language (vocabulary, phonetics, grammar, spelling) are practically repeated in the sentence. Thus, working on a sentence is the main form of language acquisition. However, the practical orientation of teaching does not exclude the study of grammar elements that generalize certain linguistic phenomena. Skillfully selected grammatical information, rules help students in practical mastery of the language.

The most problematic and difficult topics for schoolchildren when studying Russian as a foreign language are the complex expression of grammatical meanings at the end; case system; the presence of variable parts of speech; the presence in the structure of the word of prefixes, suffixes, endings; category of verb aspect; unidirectional and multidirectional verbs of motion. When studying and consolidating these topics, different types of exercises are offered. These topics are considered very difficult for elementary grades and are suggested to be studied only by senior grades. And also the greatest difficulty in learning Russian as a foreign language on the part of schoolchildren is the equivalent vocabulary, which does not exist in other languages and cultures.

There are significant reasons that lead to the emergence of certain problems in the study of Russian as a foreign language. They are associated with the peculiarities of the phonetic, grammatical and lexical level of the Russian language. Therefore, when teaching the Russian language to schoolchildren, the likelihood of such problems must be taken into

account in order to reduce them, as well as to achieve the highest result in the study of the material by schoolchildren and the use of acquired knowledge for communicative purposes.

The main trend that characterizes the initial learning process in a modern school is the focus of the entire learning process not only on imparting knowledge and instilling skills and abilities in children, but, above all, on developing the personality of students. In this regard, it is clear that the special importance of taking into account the mental characteristics of children of primary school age is clear: after all, it is in the primary grades that the foundation for the formation of a new person is laid, the basis for the subsequent assimilation of knowledge and mastery of skills is created. Primary school is designed to provide all children with the necessary level of intellectual development, to give elementary knowledge of the basics of science, to form their initial educational and general labor skills and abilities, to arouse interest in artistic and human creativity. To meet the individual needs of students, to develop their creative abilities, individual programs are introduced, extra-curricular activities and electives, technical classrooms and electives are created, schools (classes) with in-depth study of individual subjects, gymnasiums and lyceums are created. According to Sh. A. Amonashvili, a child already from birth inherits the ability to speak, to master speech. A two-year-old child already communicates with others. He could speak two or three languages at once if the people who care for him and educate him created different environments for him. So, if the mother spoke to the child in Georgian, the father in Russian, the grandmother in English, then the child would easily begin to speak with each of them in the language in which they speak with him, without confusing languages and not even understanding at first that he speaks different languages. Such examples are not uncommon in our reality. Why does it become more difficult for children older than 8-11 years to master a second language? The fact is that by the age of 6-8 years, the child freely masters speech in his native language, freely communicates with people, and the unique properties inherent in the mechanism of the ability to speak freeze (!), since they have already ensured the viability of the organism in the environment and their purpose for the body is exhausted. The other 10 years are learned no longer on the basis of the innate properties of the speech function, not by themselves, but in the process of purposeful learning and learning based on the action of memory, languages after thinking, will. For successful assimilation of program material in the primary grades, the student must have a relatively high level of observation, voluntary memorization, and organized attention; be able to analyze, generalize, reason. As shown by special studies of children 7-9 years old, they have real opportunities for this. All cognitive processes occurring in younger students are specific. Knowing them is necessary to make learning more rational and effective. In the psyche of a child of 7-9 years old, the processes of direct cognition of the surrounding world of sensation and perception are developing especially actively. Along with sharpness, freshness, brightness, concreteness and figurativeness, the most characteristic feature of the perception of younger schoolchildren in his small classes is a closely general "grasping" of an object and phenomenon. Children have their own weakness of in-depth, organized and focused analysis during perception.

Perception in primary students is associated with actions. And they perceive basically what is close, accessible and interesting to them, therefore their perception is emotional, impulsive. Hence, another feature of the perception of younger students is that visual, bright, living things are perceived better, more emotionally than, for example, symbolic and schematic images, "neutral material". Gradually, in the process of properly organized learning,

their perception becomes purposeful and manageable, more analyzing, differentiating, and takes on the character of observation. In this regard, the proportion of comparison increases, while the process of observation includes an explanation and assessment of what is seen, thereby actively developing speech. Visualization at the initial stage is used in the semantization of words and expressions (mainly subject pictures), teaching pronunciation (auditory clarity, showing articulation), setting up exercises for the development of speech (plot and situational pictures). Listening to tape recordings of Russian syllables, words and sentences is especially important for rural schools, where sometimes the Russian language environment is completely absent and children hear Russian speech only from the teacher's mouth. Tape recording thus provides another source for teaching pronunciation by imitation. However, imitation is not the most effective technique for teaching pronunciation. Much more effective is auditory-visual imitation, when children perceive sounds by seeing the teacher's face, following his articulation. And, finally, the most effective is the accompanying auditory-visual imitation and description of the articulation of a particular phoneme, comparing it with the phoneme of the native language (linguistic visualization). From this point of view, phonetic tables "Speak correctly" for elementary grades (authors K. S. Koblov, A. K. Dalimov) serve as an effective tool. not due to the fact that the age feature of younger schoolchildren is the weakness of voluntary attention, its low stability, in the elementary grades frequent transitions from one task to another are bypassed. A variety of types of work stimulates the stability of attention, short pauses relieve fatigue in children. In children 7-9 years old, there is an age-related relative predominance of the activity of the first signal system, therefore visual-figurative memory is more developed than the so-called verbal-logical. The foregoing explains the fact that younger students are prone to rote memorization and repeated repetition of perceived material. The imitation of many actions of children's utterances is memorization and is an important source of success in initial learning. Due to the underdevelopment of speech, it is easier for children to reproduce something verbatim than to convey the general meaning in their own words. That is why the teacher is obliged in every possible way to stimulate the development of the semantic memory of students, to teach them to break the material into semantic parts, to highlight the main thoughts, to draw up a logical plan of the text, to modify it, to present it. in your own words. The thinking of primary school students is characterized by a change in it in the learning process. Analytical-synthetic activity at the beginning of primary school age is basically elementary. However, by the end of the 4th grade, students, with proper training, can rise to a higher level of mental analysis (for example, in the phenomena being studied, they learn to highlight the essential features and properties of objects). A specific feature of the psyche of younger schoolchildren is also that, joining the knowledge, they continue to play. At the same time, the naive-play nature of cognition reveals enormous formal possibilities for the development of children's intellect (memorization function). Thanks to the playful approach to the environment, children easily master complex mental operations. The same age feature gives space. The same age feature gives scope for training the formal side of thinking, largely determines the naturalness, immediacy, ease of assimilation of various impressions. Appeal to the game contributes to solving the problem of continuity between school and kindergarten. In the guidelines for the Russian language textbooks for the primary grades of the Uzbek school, the game is considered as a means of teaching and developing speech. The main purpose of games is the development of comprehension and speaking skills. However, gaming exercises should not be

abused. Game and entertaining elements are positively evaluated by children when they are given within training sessions and facilitate hard work. Therefore, if in the 2nd grade the teaching side of the game is veiled, hidden, then in the 3rd-4th grades the didactic aspect of the game comes to the fore. serious educational. In other words, a reasonable combination of all types of games that “work” for language acquisition is considered legitimate (games - dramatization, role-playing, round dance, outdoor games - competitions); from learning in the game, students should gradually be included in real situations.

The game, along with a generalizing conversation, dialogue, work on the text (a short story, a fairy tale, a poem, a song) should be one of the components of the lesson. So, children in the primary grades should play, but not flirt. The success of classes is also increased through the use of dolls, toy utensils, furniture, doll clothes, and especially various crafts made from plasticine, paper, and natural materials made by the students themselves as visual aids. Here, probably, one of the interesting regularities arising from the studies of I. M. Sechenov, B. G. Ananyev, A. V. Zaporozhets, L. F. Fomina is manifested, namely: the expediency of more active use of the body's reserves at the initial stage of work, in particular touch, sensations. The problem of the pace of speech is closely related to the problem of the pace of work. It has been experimentally established that with a slow pace of oral speech, its understanding significantly worsens (O. V. Polozhishnikova), apparently due to distraction of attention. On the other hand, the normal pace of foreign language speech seems too fast for students, especially if the language material used in the speech is not yet firmly fixed. Therefore, when teaching speech perception by ear, it is necessary to vary the rate of speech depending on the difficulty of the material contained in it. In general, the methodological system of the initial teaching of the Russian language is based on the consciously - communicative principle of teaching. He aims at such an organization of the educational process, in which, on the one hand, a conscious assimilation of linguistic and speech material by students is achieved, and on the other hand, it comes to the fore as a means of communication.

References:

1. Андриянова В.И. Обучение русскому языку в школах Узбекистана на современном этапе. Т.: Укитувчи, 1997.
2. Буржунов Г.Г. Методика преподавания русского языка в начальной национальной школе. Л.: Просвещение, 1980.
3. Ильин Е. Н. Искусство общения. М.: Просвещение, 1982.
4. Методика начального обучения русскому языку в национальной школе. /Под редакцией И.В.Баранникова, А.И.Греул. Л.: Просвещение, 1984.
- 5.Хавронина С.А., Балыхина Т.М. Инновационный учебно - методический комплекс «Русский язык как иностранный». Учебное пособие. - М.: РУДН, 2008.
6. Шибко Н.Л. Методика обучения русскому языку как иностранному: учебно - методический комплекс для студентов - иностранцев нефилологических специальностей. - Минск: БГУ, 2011.
7. Ильин Е. Н. Искусство общения. М.: Просвещение, 1982.
8. Методика начального обучения русскому языку в национальной школе. /Под редакцией И.В.Баранникова, А.И.Греул. Л.: Просвещение, 1984.

9.Хавронина С.А., Балыхина Т.М. Инновационный учебно - методический комплекс «Русский язык как иностранный». Учебное пособие. - М.: РУДН, 2008.

10. Шибко Н.Л. Методика обучения русскому языку как иностранному: учебно - методический комплекс для студентов - иностранцев нефилологических специальностей. - Минск: БГУ, 2011.

